

A red line-art sketch of a building with multiple windows and a street scene with trees and vehicles. The drawing is done in a simple, sketchy style.

**ArXiv in the open access era : it's use and Impact on
physics researches**

BY

M.N. NAGARAJ

Assistant Librarian Raman Research Institute, Bangalore

Kamela

How to provide open access?

Two routes to Open Access:

- Publish in Open Access Journals – (**Gold Route**)
 - Publish in fully OA journals
 - Hybrid OA Journals
- Publish in Non-Open Access Journals & Self-Archive (**Green Route**)
 - In Discipline Based Central Archives
 - In Institutional Archives – (Often not the published version)

OA Resources Providers

- **Authors**

**Self-archiving, Personal webpage or Blog,
ResearchGate**

- **Publishers**

OA journals (Hybrid & Open) (DOAJ)

With APC (Commercial Publishers)

- **Libraries**

**Institutional Repositories -Directory of open access repositories (DOAR)
Society, Academy & University**

arXiv, HAL (open archive), ETD Repository,

Database, (NASA/ADS & INSPIRE-HEP)

OA journals (without APC, e.g Pramana, Current Science)

Type of site	Science
Available in	English
Owner	<u>Cornell University</u>
Created by	<u>Paul Ginsparg</u>
Website	<u>arXiv.org</u>
Alexa rank	3,547 (as of September 2016) ^[1] 25 1,724 (Global Rank) (as of 29th March 2017) ^[1]
Commercial	No
Launched	August 14, 1991; 29.8 years ago
Current status	Online

Paul Ginsparg

Ranking of arXiv

An amazon.com company

SOLUTIONS ▾ TOOLS ▾ PRICING

This site ranks:

1,894

In global internet traffic and engagement over the past 90 days

↗ 499

Country Alexa Rank

us United Sta... ▾

1,538

[Improving your Alexa Rank](#)

All visitors to this site in the past 30 days

Visitors by Country

us United States	26.6%
cn China	13.6%
in India	12.5%

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Growth of arXiv

arXiv submission rate statistics

Data for 1991 through 2019, updated 1 January 2021.

Left: number of new submissions/year as a function of calendar year for "hep" = High Energy Physics (hep-th+hep-ph+hep-lat+hep-ex), "cond-mat" = Condensed Matter Physics, "astro-ph" = Astrophysics, "other physics" = physics+nucl+gr-qc+quant-ph+nlin, "math" = Mathematics (math+math-ph), cs, eess, stats, biology = q-bio, finance = q

More than 1,887,161 scholarly articles (2021)

Methodology

- **Survey method** - Structured questionnaire was designed & distributed to researchers.
- The questionnaire consists of five segments.
 - Demographic data,
 - Awareness,
 - Usage
 - Impact , satisfaction

Open Access Resources

- **arXiv**
- **NASA/ADS database**
- **Fully open access journals in physics (DOAJ listed)**
- **Hybrid open access journals in Physics**
- **INSPIRE-High Energy Physics (database)**
- **SCOAP³ journal articles repository (Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics)**
- **Institutional Repositories (IR)**

Hypotheses

- Use of OA resources depends on field of research of physics researchers
- There is significant relationship between designation of researchers & purpose of use of open access resources
- **There is significant impact on physics researches by contributing to arXiv.**
- Physics researchers are satisfied with all the available OA resources
- There is significant relationship between age of researcher & awareness of IR

Population Surveyed

Sl. NO.	Institute	Questionnaire Distributed	Response Received	Percentage
1	RRI	120	102	85
2	IISc	140	98	70
3	IIA	110	69	62.72
4	JNCASR	80	60	75
5	CNES	30	23	73
		480	352	73.33

Response by Designation

Research Institute	Number of Response				Total
	JRF	SRF	Postdoc	Faculty	
	Count	Count	Count	Count	
IISC	14	44	14	26	98
RRI	19	31	11	41	102
IIA	15	15	8	31	69
JNCASR	12	21	14	13	60
CeNS	4	9	1	9	23
Total	64	120	48	120	352
Percentage	19	34	13	34	100

Research field wise Response

■ Responses	112	22	20	124	51	23
■ Percentage	31.8	6.3	5.7	35.2	14.5	6.5

n=352

preferred mode for Searching Information

	Google	Google Scholar	Publishers site	IR	arXiv	NASA/A DS	
■ Frequency	141	80	14	1	40	76	
■ Percent	40.1	22.7	4.0	.3	11.4	21.6	

n=352

arXiv@25 by Survey Report
by Rieger, Oya Yildirim , Cornell University
Study report in June 28th 2016

To **access papers** directly arXiv website (79%) Google (50%) and Google Scholar (35%)

To **discover content** 63% users to the link for new under particular category another 63% enter author name and search term. Only 14% rely on mailing list

Rely on **other services** to interact with arXiv - like **ADS, INSPIRE, Google Scholar**

User awareness of OA publishing

**28 = 8%
Respondents
are not aware of
any types of OA**

	Self-archiving	Paid OA	Green OA	Gold OA	CCC	Delayed OA
Awareness	304	169	30	28	141	114
Percent Aware	86.4	48	8.5	8	40.1	32.4
Percent Un Aware	13.6	52	91.5	92	59.9	67.6

Use of OA Resources

Open Access Resources	Frequently	Some time	Rarely	Never Used	Total Usage
ArXiv preprint repository	66(64.7)	20(19.6)	7(6.86)	9(8.82)	91.18
NASA/ADS database	27(26.4)	12(11.7)	10(9.80)	53(51.97)	48.03
Fully open access journals in physics (DOAJ listed journals)	28(27.4)	46(45.1)	12(11.76)	16(15.69)	84.31
Hybrid open access journals in physics	48(47.0)	21(20.5)	8(7.84)	25(24.51)	75.49
inSPIRE –High Energy Physics database	4(3.92)	8(7.84)	3(2.94)	87(85.30)	14.70
SCOAP ³ Journal articles Repository /e.g. The European Physical Journal C (EPJC) JHEP , Nuclear Physics B	4(3.92)	7(6.86)	7(6.86)	84(82.36)	17.64
Institutional Repositories (IR)	16(15.6)	34(33.3)	14(13.73)	38(37.25)	62.75

Use of arXiv based on their research field.

ArXiv Usage & Awareness	A&A	HEP	Optics	CMP	TP	Biophysics	Total	Percentage
Never used	0	0	3(15%)	12(9.68%)	0	0	15	4.3%
Aware but not used	0	0	1(5%)	2(1.61%)	0	3(13.04%)	6	1.7%
Rarely	8(7.15%)	2(9.10%)	2(10%)	7(5.65%)	0	1(4.35%)	20	5.7%
Sometime	15(13.39%)	5(22.82%)	4(20%)	28(22.58%)	7(13.73%)	6(26.09%)	65	18.5%
Frequently	89(79.46%)	15(68.10%)	10(50%)	75(60.48%)	44(86.27%)	13(56.52%)	246	69.8%
Total	112 (100%)	22(100%)	20(100%)	124(100%)	51(100%)	23(100%)	352	100%
% of Total	31.8%	6.3%	5.7%	35.2%	14.5%	6.5%	100.0%	

Purpose of Use

SL NO	Physics Researchers	Purpose of use of OA Resources (arXiv and OA Jouranls)	Chi Square Test	Significance	Relationship exists for Purpose of Use of OA Resource
1	Designation	Teaching	X2(12) =105.710 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
2	Designation	Current Awareness	X2(12) =21.141 P=0.04	Significant	Yes
3	Designation	Research	X2(12) =41.001 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
4	Designation	To write article	X2(12) =37.547 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
5	Designation	Prepare for Exam	X2(12) =145.917 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
6	Designation	Study for Course Work	X2(12) =165.894 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
7	Designation	Project work	X2(12) =48.773 P=0.00	Highly	Yes
8	Designation	To Guide others	X2(12) =39.357 P=0.00	Highly	Yes

Figure showing contribution to arXiv

60% are contributing to arXiv

There is significant impact on physics researches by contributing to arXiv preprint open access repository.

SL NO	Physics Researchers	Impact due to contribution to arXiv	Chi Square Test	Significance	Relationship exists due to contribution
1	Research Experience	Feedback received for contributing articles	$X^2(36) = 89.674$ P=0.00	Highly	Yes
2	Research Experience	Resulted in collaboration	$X^2(36) = 94.267$ P=0.00	Highly	Yes
3	Research Experience	Resulted in faster revision	$X^2(42) = 94.810$ P=0.00	Highly	Yes
4	Research Experience	Helped to improve results	$X^2(36) = 107.963$ P=0.00	Highly	Yes
5	Research Experience	Increased number of citations	$X^2(36) = 98.551$ P=0.00	Highly	Yes

Got good feedback for article		Research Experience in years						Total	
		<1	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-25		26 Above
Not Published	Count	16	63	26	5	3	0	4	117
	%	94.1%	44.1%	35.1%	19.2%	9.1%	0.0%	10.5%	33.2%
No Influence	Count	0	10	7	3	4	2	6	32
	%	0.0%	7.0%	9.5%	11.5%	12.1%	9.5%	15.8%	9.1%
Very Limited extent	Count	0	12	6	4	7	7	5	41
	%	0.0%	8.4%	8.1%	15.4%	21.2%	33.3%	13.2%	11.6%
Uncertain	Count	0	3	0	1	0	0	2	6
	%	0.0%	2.1%	0.0%	3.8%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	1.7%
Some extent	Count	0	31	13	7	7	4	9	71
	%	0.0%	21.7%	17.6%	26.9%	21.2%	19.0%	23.7%	20.2%
Full Extent	Count	1	21	20	6	10	6	10	74
	%	5.9%	14.7%	27.0%	23.1%	30.3%	28.6%	26.3%	21.0%
Not contribute d Papers	Count	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	11
	%	0.0%	2.1%	2.7%	0.0%	6.1%	9.5%	5.3%	3.1%
Total With percentage	Count	17	143	74	26	33	21	38	352
	% within RExp	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

53% got feedback

Contribution helped to increase number of citations		Research Experience in years							Total
		<1	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-25	26 Above	
Not Published	Count	16	47	20	4	3	0	2	92
	%	94.1%	32.9%	27.0%	15.4%	9.1%	0.0%	5.3%	26.1%
No Influence	Count	1	12	7	6	2	1	3	32
	%	5.9%	8.4%	9.5%	23.1%	6.1%	4.8%	7.9%	9.1%
Very Limited extent	Count	0	1	5	3	2	1	4	16
	%	0.0%	.7%	6.8%	11.5%	6.1%	4.8%	10.5%	4.5%
Uncertain	Count	0	8	6	1	4	1	6	26
	%	0.0%	5.6%	8.1%	3.8%	12.1%	4.8%	15.8%	7.4%
Some extent	Count	0	30	15	4	10	5	6	70
	%	0.0%	21.0%	20.3%	15.4%	30.3%	23.8%	15.8%	19.9%
Full Extent	Count	0	42	19	8	11	11	14	105
	%	0.0%	29.4%	25.7%	30.8%	33.3%	52.4%	36.8%	29.8%
Not contributed papers	Count	0	3	2	0	1	2	3	11
	%	0.0%	2.1%	2.7%	0.0%	3.0%	9.5%	7.9%	3.1%
Total with % Research Experience	Count	17	143	74	26	33	21	38	352
	% within RExp	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

54% got increased in citations

Citing arXiv as reference

59.7% are Citing

arXiv is platform to communicate research results

Around 80% agree to full extent

93.5% are satisfied

Owning the copyright of publications

Use and Awareness of Open Access Journals among Physics Researchers in Bangalore City: A Study

Nagaraj M. N.

Assistant Librarian,
Raman Research Institute, C V Raman Avenue,
Sadashivanagar, Bangalore-560080. India.
nagaraj@rri.res.in Contact-9886096428

M. K. Bhandi

University Librarian,
Mangalore University,
Mangalore-574 199,
Karnataka, India

Prakash

Indian Academy of Sciences (IASc),
C V Raman Avenue,
Sadashivanagar,
Bangalore-560080. India.

ABSTRACT

Open access (OA) journals have emerged as an alternative to the subscription model for journals. Researchers need to look at several aspects of OA journals before publishing their work some of the aspects are reputation of the journal, relevance of journal content, quality of peer review and journal's impact factor. This paper deals with awareness and use of open access journals by physics researchers. A structured questionnaire was distributed to 480 physics researchers and we were able to get 352

Influencing factors to publish in OA journals

SL No	Factors	Responses	Percentage	Rank	
1	Reputation of the Journal	Yes	114	57.0%	3
		No	84	42.0%	
		Don't Know	2	1.0%	
2	Relevance of Journal content	Yes	102	51.0%	4
		No	96	48.0%	
		Don't Know	2	1.0%	
3	Quality of Peer review	Yes	139	69.5%	1
		No	59	29.5%	
		Don't Know	2	1.0%	
4	Journal's Impact Factor	Yes	132	66.0%	2
		No	66	33.0%	
		Don't Know	2	1.0%	
5	Don't Know any of the above	Yes	9	4.5%	5
		No	191	95.5%	

2019 Impact factor

- Physical Review D – IF – 4.833
- Physical Review Letters – 8.885
- Physical Review X (PRX) – **12.577** (OA Journal)

- OA is disruptive invention it may be giving threat to Commercial Publishers
- Publishers have taken Lateral entry (APC charges)
- Hybrid OA more profitable to publishers

Conclusion

- ArXiv preprint repository is driven by authors through self-archiving. This study also shows that 86.4% are aware of self-archiving their publications
- Out of 352 respondents 313(94%) are using arXiv preprint repository
- This study shows that around 60% are citing arXiv, which is a positive impact of usage of OA resource.
- This study also shows that 93.5% are satisfied with arXiv and grade it as excellent and good and only 6.5% are not satisfied.

Contd.

- arXiv is not only extensively used but it is also cited thus indicating positive perception.
- Physics researchers have high level of awareness and use of OA resources
- Most of the physics researchers (80%) accept that there is a **fundamental benefit in open access publishing**

Contd.

- Usage and its satisfaction by researchers substantiate efforts made by OA resource managing organisations including library.
- Ultimately, the success of OA resource depends on the users. Through this study physics researchers who have not used the OA resources got awareness and started using it

Areas for further research

1. Similar study can be carried out in other fields like medicine and biology
2. The impact of OA resources on library workload and budget
3. Awareness of copyright issue and its impact on OA publishing
4. Citation impact of OA publishing in physics literature
5. Evaluation study of OA resources in Physics literature
6. It is recommended to carry out research on use and impact of predatory OA Journals

Papers Published

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